

Online Appendix

A Bayesian Approach to Probability Default Model Calibration: Theoretical and Empirical Insights on the Jeffreys Test

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A An illustration of Bayesian and frequentist approaches

The Bayesian approach provides a systematic framework for updating beliefs about unknown quantities based on observed data. Suppose we wish to estimate the probability of rain tomorrow, denoted by θ . Based on historical data, we believe that it rains 30% of the time, and this belief is represented by a Beta prior distribution $p(\theta) = \text{Beta}(3, 7)$. The prior mean is given by:

$$\mathbb{E}[\theta] = \frac{\alpha}{\alpha + \beta} = 0.3, \quad (\text{A1})$$

reflecting moderate confidence in this initial belief.

Now, assume we observe new evidence: dark clouds, which historically lead to rain 80% of the time ($p(\text{dark clouds} \mid \theta = 1) = 0.8$) and no rain 20% of the time ($p(\text{dark clouds} \mid \theta = 0) = 0.2$). Using this evidence, we apply Bayes' theorem to update our prior belief about θ . For a Beta prior combined with a binomial likelihood, the posterior distribution remains a Beta distribution:

$$\Pr(\theta \mid \text{dark clouds}) = \text{Beta}(\alpha + \text{successes}, \beta + \text{failures}). \quad (\text{A2})$$

Assuming that observing dark clouds corresponds to one "success," the posterior becomes

$$\Pr(\theta \mid \text{dark clouds}) = \text{Beta}(4, 7). \quad (\text{A3})$$

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The posterior mean is then equal to:

$$\mathbb{E}[\theta \mid \text{dark clouds}] = \frac{\alpha + \text{successes}}{\alpha + \beta + \text{observations}} = \frac{4}{4 + 7} \approx 0.36, \quad (\text{A4})$$

indicating that after observing dark clouds, our updated belief about the probability of rain increases slightly, combining prior information and new evidence.

In contrast, the frequentist approach treats θ as a fixed but unknown parameter. A frequentist would rely solely on the observed data. For instance, if we observed dark clouds on 10 days, with rain occurring on 4 of those days, the maximum likelihood estimate (MLE) of θ is

$$\hat{\theta} = \frac{\text{Number of rainy days}}{\text{Total number of days}} = \frac{4}{10} = 0.4. \quad (\text{A5})$$

Uncertainty in this estimate would be expressed through confidence intervals. Using a normal approximation, a 95% confidence interval for θ is given by:

$$\hat{\theta} \pm 1.96 \sqrt{\frac{\hat{\theta}(1 - \hat{\theta})}{n}} = 0.4 \pm 1.96 \sqrt{\frac{0.4 \times 0.6}{10}} \approx [0.25, 0.55]. \quad (\text{A6})$$

B Conjugacy of the Beta prior

We now show that the $\text{Beta}(\alpha, \beta)$ distribution is a conjugate prior for the probability of default p_k when defaults follow a binomial model. Let $\mathbf{y} = (y_1, \dots, y_{n_k})$ denote the backtesting sample for the risk grade G_k , where $y_i = 1$ if default occurs and 0 otherwise. Under the assumption that defaults are independent and identically distributed, the likelihood function is:

$$L_{n_k}(p_k; \mathbf{y}) \equiv \pi(\mathbf{y} \mid p_k) = p_k^{\sum y_i} (1 - p_k)^{n_k - \sum y_i}. \quad (\text{A7})$$

Suppose that the prior distribution of p_k is $\text{Beta}(\alpha, \beta)$, with density:

$$\pi(p_k) = \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + \beta)}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} p_k^{\alpha-1} (1 - p_k)^{\beta-1}, \quad (\text{A8})$$

where $\Gamma(\cdot)$ denotes the Gamma function.

Using Bayes' theorem, the unnormalized posterior distribution is proportional to the product of the likelihood and the prior:

$$\pi(p_k \mid \mathbf{y}) \propto L_{n_k}(p_k; \mathbf{y}) \times \pi(p_k; \alpha, \beta), \quad (\text{A9})$$

Thus, the unnormalized posterior is given by:

$$\pi(p_k \mid \mathbf{y}) \propto p_k^{\sum y_i} (1 - p_k)^{n_k - \sum y_i} \times p_k^{\alpha-1} (1 - p_k)^{\beta-1} = p_k^{\alpha + \sum y_i - 1} (1 - p_k)^{\beta + n_k - \sum y_i - 1}. \quad (\text{A10})$$

Let $d_k = \sum y_i$ denote the number of observed defaults in the sample, we have:

$$\pi(p_k | \mathbf{y}) \propto p_k^{\alpha+d_k-1} (1-p_k)^{\beta+n_k-d_k-1} \quad (\text{A11})$$

We recognize the kernel of a Beta distribution.

$$\pi(p_k | \mathbf{y}) = \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + \beta + n_k)}{\Gamma(\alpha + d_k)\Gamma(\beta + n_k - d_k)} p_k^{\alpha+d_k-1} (1-p_k)^{\beta+n_k-d_k-1}, \quad p_k \in [0, 1], \quad (\text{A12})$$

Therefore, the posterior distribution is also a Beta distribution, like the prior distribution:

$$p_k | \mathbf{y} \sim \text{Beta}(\alpha + d_k, \beta + n_k - d_k), \quad (\text{A13})$$

This shows that the Beta distribution is a *conjugate prior* for the binomial model: the posterior distribution remains in the Beta family, with updated parameters depending on the observed data in the backtesting sample.

C Construction of the Jeffreys prior

The Jeffreys prior provides a principled method for constructing a non-informative prior, based on the Fisher information. Recall that for a model with parameter space $\Theta \subseteq \mathbb{R}$, under regularity conditions, the Fisher information is defined by:

$$\mathcal{I}(\theta) = -\mathbb{E}_\theta \left(\frac{\partial^2 \log f(x | \theta)}{\partial \theta^2} \right). \quad (\text{A14})$$

where $f(x | \theta)$ is the likelihood, and the expectation is taken with respect to $f(x | \theta)$.

The Jeffreys prior for θ is proportional to the Fisher information and then defined as:

$$\pi(\theta) \propto \sqrt{\mathcal{I}(\theta)}, \quad (\text{A15})$$

meaning that the prior is proportional to the square root of the Fisher information. This construction ensures that the prior is invariant under reparameterizations and aims to minimize the influence of the prior relative to the information contained in the data.

In our case, we are interested in the probability of default p_k , with the data following a binomial distribution:

$$D_k \sim \text{Binomial}(n_k, p_k), \quad (\text{A16})$$

where D_k denotes the number of defaults observed among n_k borrowers in risk grade G_k . The likelihood function for p_k given the observations \mathbf{y} is:

$$L_{n_k}(p_k; \mathbf{y}) \equiv \pi(\mathbf{y} | p_k) = \binom{n_k}{d_k} p_k^{d_k} (1-p_k)^{n_k-d_k}. \quad (\text{A17})$$

Taking the second derivative of the log-likelihood with respect to p_k gives:

$$\frac{\partial^2 \log L_{n_k}(p_k; \mathbf{y})}{\partial p_k^2} = -\frac{d_k}{p_k^2} - \frac{n_k - d_k}{(1 - p_k)^2}. \quad (\text{A18})$$

Thus, the Fisher information for p_k is:

$$\mathcal{I}(p_k) = \mathbb{E} \left(-\frac{\partial^2 \log L_{n_k}(p_k; \mathbf{y})}{\partial p_k^2} \right) = \frac{n_k}{p_k(1 - p_k)}. \quad (\text{A19})$$

Applying the definition of the Jeffreys prior, we obtain:

$$\pi(p_k) \propto p_k^{-1/2} (1 - p_k)^{-1/2}. \quad (\text{A20})$$

This is recognized as the kernel of a Beta distribution with parameters 0.5 and 0.5:

$$p_k \sim \text{Beta} \left(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2} \right), \quad (\text{A21})$$

which a pdf equal to:

$$\pi(p_k) = \frac{\Gamma(1)}{\Gamma(\frac{1}{2})\Gamma(\frac{1}{2})} p_k^{-\frac{1}{2}} (1 - p_k)^{-\frac{1}{2}}, \quad (\text{A22})$$

Therefore, the Jeffreys prior for the probability of default p_k is a Beta $(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})$ distribution. This prior is non-informative in the sense that it minimizes the prior influence and reflects maximum uncertainty about p_k before observing any data.

D Highest Density Region and Equal-Tailed Credible Intervals

Given a posterior density $f_{p_k|\mathbf{y}}(p)$ for the parameter p_k , the $(1 - \alpha)$ Highest Density Region (HDR) is defined as the set:

$$\text{HDR}_{1-\alpha}(p_k) = \{p : f_{p_k|\mathbf{y}}(p) \geq c_\alpha\}, \quad (\text{A23})$$

where the threshold c_α is chosen such that:

$$\int_{\text{HDR}_{1-\alpha}(p_k)} f_{p_k|\mathbf{y}}(p) dp = 1 - \alpha. \quad (\text{A24})$$

This construction ensures that every point within the HDR has at least as high posterior density as any point outside the region. For unimodal posteriors, such as standard Beta distributions encountered in PD calibration, the HDR reduces to a single continuous interval corresponding to the highest-probability values.

The Equal-Tailed Credible Interval (ETCI) for level $(1 - \alpha)$ is the interval $[p_L, p_U]$ such that:

$$\Pr(p_k \leq p_L | \mathbf{y}) = \frac{\alpha}{2}, \quad \Pr(p_k \geq p_U | \mathbf{y}) = \frac{\alpha}{2}, \quad (\text{A25})$$

with p_L and p_U computed by inverting the cumulative distribution function of the posterior.

While both intervals contain the same posterior mass, their coverage can differ when the posterior is highly asymmetric or multimodal. The HDR always provides the shortest region containing the specified probability mass and focuses strictly on the regions of highest density. In contrast, the ETCI allocates probability equally to both tails, which can result in the inclusion of lower-density regions, particularly in bimodal or highly skewed cases.

Figure A1 displays a bimodal posterior distribution for p_k , along with the corresponding 95% HDR and ETCI. In this example, the HDR consists of two disjoint intervals that capture the peaks of the distribution, whereas the ETCI forms a single central interval that may include low-density regions between the modes. This illustrates that, while the two approaches are nearly equivalent in the unimodal Beta case, they can diverge significantly when the posterior departs from unimodality or symmetry.

Figure A1: Comparison between the Highest Density Region (HDR) and the Equal-Tailed Credible Interval (ETCI) for a bimodal mixture distribution. The HDR (shaded blue, left) includes only the highest-probability regions, while the ETCI (shaded orange, right) symmetrically covers the central 95% of the posterior mass, possibly including low-density areas between the modes.

E Prior choice in Bayesian PD calibration: comparison and sensitivity

This appendix complements the main text by positioning the Jeffreys prior relative to other canonical non-informative Beta priors in the binomial PD calibration setting, and by quantifying the sensitivity of Bayesian credible intervals to prior choice in regimes that are operationally relevant for PD backtesting (low default rates and small cohorts).

E.1 Non-informative Beta priors for a binomial PD

Let p_k denote the grade-level default probability and let

$$D_k \mid p_k \sim \text{Binomial}(n_k, p_k), \quad p_k \sim \text{Beta}(\alpha, \beta).$$

The posterior is conjugate and given by

$$p_k \mid D_k = d_k \sim \text{Beta}(\alpha + d_k, \beta + n_k - d_k).$$

Within this framework, several priors are commonly described as “non-informative”. In PD calibration, their practical differences concentrate in the boundary region $p_k \in \{0, 1\}$, which is precisely the region that governs low-default grades, where outcomes $D_k \in \{0, n_k\}$ are comparatively frequent. We focus on three canonical choices:

- **Bayes–Laplace prior** $\text{Beta}(1, 1)$, uniform on p_k , which can be interpreted as adding one pseudo-default and one pseudo-non-default.
- **Haldane prior** $\pi(p_k) \propto [p_k(1-p_k)]^{-1}$, which is improper and is therefore considered through the stress-test approximation $\text{Beta}(\varepsilon, \varepsilon)$ for small ε .
- **Jeffreys prior** $\text{Beta}(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})$, derived from Fisher information and invariant under smooth one-to-one reparameterizations.

Figure A2 contrasts the corresponding prior densities. The Haldane-type prior concentrates sharply at the boundaries and can therefore produce overly sharp posterior statements in small samples. Jeffreys remains less boundary-concentrated while retaining invariance, and Bayes–Laplace is comparatively more regular near 0 and 1.

E.2 Why Jeffreys yields near-nominal finite-sample coverage

Our use of Jeffreys is not motivated by “flatness” but by two properties that align with model validation practice.

Probability matching. Jeffreys is the canonical *probability-matching* prior for regular one-parameter models: posterior quantiles induced by $\pi(\theta) \propto \sqrt{I(\theta)}$ match nominal frequentist coverage up to higher order (coverage error of order $O(n_k^{-1})$); see, e.g., [Welch and Peers \(1963\)](#); [Ghosh \(2011\)](#). In the binomial case, this property provides a principled explanation for why Jeffreys equal-tailed credible intervals tend to remain close to nominal coverage in finite samples, consistent with classical binomial evidence surveyed by [Brown et al. \(2001\)](#).

Invariance and auditability. Jeffreys is invariant under smooth one-to-one reparameterizations. This is operationally relevant in regulated PD calibration because different implementations may express the same binomial model on different scales (e.g., probability p_k , logit $\eta_k = \log\{p_k/(1-p_k)\}$),

Figure A2: $\text{Beta}(\alpha, \beta)$ prior densities for a binomial default probability $p \in (0, 1)$. Top row: Jeffreys $\text{Beta}(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})$ and Bayes–Laplace $\text{Beta}(1, 1)$. Bottom-right: Haldane-type approximation $\text{Beta}(\varepsilon, \varepsilon)$ with $\varepsilon = 10^{-3}$, illustrating the extreme boundary concentration relevant when $D \in \{0, n\}$ in low-default grades.

or other monotone transforms). With non-invariant priors (e.g., uniform in p_k), two implementations can produce different posterior bounds—and therefore different calibration conclusions—solely due to a parameterization choice. Jeffreys removes this implementation-driven variability by construction, which simplifies audit trails and reduces avoidable model risk.

E.3 Prior-sensitivity Monte Carlo: coverage of Bayesian credible intervals

To quantify the practical impact of prior choice in regimes relevant for PD calibration, we replicate the binomial Monte Carlo design under three non-informative priors: Jeffreys $\text{Beta}(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})$, Bayes–Laplace $\text{Beta}(1, 1)$, and a Haldane-type boundary stress test $\text{Beta}(\varepsilon, \varepsilon)$ with $\varepsilon = 10^{-6}$. We evaluate the empirical *frequentist* coverage of the corresponding *Bayesian* equal-tailed 95% credible intervals across grids of true PD values p and cohort sizes n .

Figures A3–A5 report coverage curves. In each panel, the dashed horizontal line indicates the nominal level (95%). The RMSE annotation summarizes the deviation of the displayed coverage

curve from the nominal level over the plotted p -range, and the minimum annotation highlights severe under-coverage when it occurs.

Rare-event window (low-default grades). Figure A3 focuses on the rare-event region $p \in [10^{-4}, 5 \times 10^{-3}]$ with $n = 1000$, representative of low-default grades. In this regime, Jeffreys and Bayes–Laplace remain close to nominal across the window, while the Haldane-type prior exhibits pronounced under-coverage at the smallest PDs, consistent with boundary-concentrated priors producing overly narrow posterior intervals when $D = 0$ occurs frequently.

Full PD range and small-sample stress test. Over $p \in [10^{-3}, 10^{-1}]$ with $n = 1000$ (Figure A4), all priors move closer to nominal on average; however, the Haldane-type prior still displays a material low-end fragility. When the cohort size is small, $n = 50$ (Figure A5), these effects become more pronounced: Haldane-type priors can yield extreme under-coverage, whereas Jeffreys and Bayes–Laplace remain substantially closer to nominal.

Figure A3: Prior sensitivity (rare-event focus): two-sided coverage curves for $n = 1000$ over $p \in [10^{-4}, 5 \times 10^{-3}]$. The dashed line is the nominal level (95%). The RMSE box reports the RMSE of the displayed coverage curve to the nominal level over the plotted p -range; the minimum annotation flags severe under-coverage when it occurs.

Figure A4: Prior sensitivity (full range): two-sided coverage curves for $n = 1000$ over $p \in [10^{-3}, 10^{-1}]$. Jeffreys and Bayes–Laplace remain close to nominal in aggregate (low RMSE), while the Haldane-type prior exhibits a low-end fragility consistent with boundary concentration.

Scenario summary. Table A1 summarizes the scenario-based results using (i) the Monte Carlo mean of the equal-tailed 95% credible bounds $[\bar{L}, \bar{U}]$, (ii) the mean interval length $\bar{\ell}$, and (iii) empirical frequentist coverage (Cvg.) along with its absolute deviation from nominal $|\Delta| = |\text{Cvg.} - 0.95|$. In the low-default and small-sample scenarios, the Haldane-type prior achieves shorter average lengths but at the cost of large under-coverage. Jeffreys delivers near-nominal coverage with mod-

Figure A5: Prior sensitivity (small-sample stress test): two-sided coverage curves for $n = 50$ over $p \in [10^{-3}, 10^{-1}]$. The Haldane-type prior produces extreme under-coverage in small samples (high RMSE and very low minimum), whereas Jeffreys and Bayes–Laplace remain substantially closer to nominal.

erate lengths, while Bayes–Laplace is comparable but can be slightly less stable in the most adverse regimes.

Table A1: Prior-sensitivity summary (two-sided 95% credible intervals): average bounds, average length, and empirical frequentist coverage.

Scenario	Jeffreys		Bayes–Laplace		Haldane-type (ε, ε)	
	$[\bar{L}, \bar{U}]$	$\bar{\ell}$	$[\bar{L}, \bar{U}]$	$\bar{\ell}$	$[\bar{L}, \bar{U}]$	$\bar{\ell}$
Baseline	[0.0051, 0.0174] (Cvg.=0.943; $ \Delta =0.007$)	0.0123	[0.0055, 0.0180] (Cvg.=0.964; $ \Delta =0.014$)	0.0126	[0.0048, 0.0168] (Cvg.=0.943; $ \Delta =0.007$)	0.0120
Low Default	[0.0002, 0.0045] (Cvg.=0.982; $ \Delta =0.032$)	0.0043	[0.0003, 0.0054] (Cvg.=0.921; $ \Delta =0.029$)	0.0051	[0.0001, 0.0030] (Cvg.=0.614; $ \Delta =0.336$)	0.0029
Small Sample	[0.0019, 0.0438] (Cvg.=0.981; $ \Delta =0.031$)	0.0419	[0.0031, 0.0528] (Cvg.=0.922; $ \Delta =0.028$)	0.0497	[0.0011, 0.0294] (Cvg.=0.610; $ \Delta =0.340$)	0.0282
Large Sample	[0.0081, 0.0120] (Cvg.=0.956; $ \Delta =0.006$)	0.0039	[0.0082, 0.0121] (Cvg.=0.954; $ \Delta =0.004$)	0.0039	[0.0081, 0.0119] (Cvg.=0.956; $ \Delta =0.006$)	0.0039

Note: For each scenario and prior, $[\bar{L}, \bar{U}]$ is the Monte Carlo mean of equal-tailed 95% credible bounds and $\bar{\ell}$ is the mean interval length. **Cvg.** denotes the empirical coverage and $|\Delta| = |\text{Cvg.} - 0.95|$ is the absolute deviation from nominal. Haldane-type uses $\varepsilon = 10^{-6}$. Scenarios: Baseline ($n = 1000, p = 0.01$), Low Default ($n = 1000, p = 0.001$), Small Sample ($n = 100, p = 0.01$), Large Sample ($n = 10,000, p = 0.01$).

Finally, we note that for the non-informative priors considered here, prior influence vanishes as n_k grows large (Bernstein–von Mises; see, e.g., van der Vaart, 1998, Ch. 10). Consequently, the practical importance of prior choice concentrates in the low-default and small-sample regimes that are central to PD calibration; the sensitivity results above document that Jeffreys is the most consistently near-nominal option in precisely these regimes.

F Monte Carlo supplements

This appendix reports three complementary diagnostics omitted from the main text for conciseness. First, we document the behavior of *one-sided* (upper) intervals, which are commonly used when

inference is summarized through an upper PD bound in low- or zero-default settings. Second, we provide a brief full-range benchmark check (in the spirit of [Brown et al., 2001](#)) to confirm that our simulation code reproduces standard coverage patterns for binomial interval estimators. Third, we assess robustness to default clustering by evaluating Binomial-based intervals under a Beta–Binomial data-generating process.

F.1 One-sided intervals

We consider one-sided upper intervals of the form $[0, U]$ at nominal level $1 - \alpha = 95\%$. For each replication, U is computed as: (i) the Jeffreys one-sided posterior quantile (ECB-style), (ii) the exact Clopper–Pearson one-sided bound, or (iii) the one-sided normal approximation. One-sided coverage is defined as the repeated-sampling probability $\Pr(p \leq U)$.

Table [A2](#) reports Monte Carlo averages of the one-sided bounds across the four scenarios used in the paper. In the baseline and small-sample configurations, the Clopper–Pearson bound is larger on average than the other two, while the normal approximation yields the smallest average bound. In the large-sample configuration, the three bounds are essentially indistinguishable.

Figures [A6](#) and [A7](#) report one-sided coverage curves over $p \in [0.001, 0.1]$ for $n = 100$ and $n = 1000$. Clopper–Pearson exhibits substantial overcoverage for small p , consistent with exact inversion. The one-sided normal approximation can display pronounced undercoverage when expected defaults are small. The Jeffreys one-sided bound approaches the nominal level as p increases, with visible oscillations induced by binomial discreteness.

Table A2: One-sided (upper) bounds (95%)

Scenario	Jeffreys	Clopper–Pearson	Normal
Baseline	(0.016) [0.000, 0.016]	(0.017) [0.000, 0.017]	(0.015) [0.000, 0.015]
Low Default	(0.004) [0.000, 0.004]	(0.005) [0.000, 0.005]	(0.002) [0.000, 0.002]
Small Sample	(0.037) [0.000, 0.037]	(0.046) [0.000, 0.046]	(0.023) [0.000, 0.023]
Large Sample	(0.011) [0.000, 0.011]	(0.011) [0.000, 0.011]	(0.011) [0.000, 0.011]

Note: Average one-sided lengths (in parentheses) and Monte Carlo mean bounds $[\bar{L}, \bar{U}]$ over $S = 10,000$ replications. Scenarios: Baseline ($n = 1000, p = 0.01$), Low Default ($n = 1000, p = 0.001$), Small Sample ($n = 100, p = 0.01$), and Large Sample ($n = 100,000, p = 0.01$).

F.2 Full-range coverage comparison ($p \in [0, 1]$)

Figure [A8](#) reports a full-range coverage comparison over $p \in [0, 1]$ with $n = 50$, using equal-tailed Jeffreys, Clopper–Pearson, and the normal approximation. The purpose is diagnostic. The resulting curves display oscillations associated with binomial discreteness, boundary distortions for the normal approximation, and conservative coverage for Clopper–Pearson, as documented in [Brown et al. \(2001\)](#).

Figure A6: One-sided empirical coverage (95%) with $n = 100$ over $p \in [0.001, 0.1]$.

Figure A7: One-sided empirical coverage (95%) with $n = 1000$ over $p \in [0.001, 0.1]$.

F.3 Beta–Binomial robustness

The main Monte Carlo experiments assume a Binomial model, which corresponds to conditional independence and within-grade homogeneity. In credit portfolios, defaults may be correlated due to shared exposures and common shocks, inducing over-dispersion relative to the Binomial variance. To assess sensitivity to such clustering, we replicate the simulations under a Beta–Binomial data-generating process,

$$\theta \sim \text{Beta}(\alpha, \beta), \quad D \mid \theta \sim \text{Binomial}(n, \theta), \quad (\text{A26})$$

with (α, β) parameterized by a target mean p and an intra-class correlation $\rho \in (0, 1)$,

$$\alpha = p \frac{1 - \rho}{\rho}, \quad \beta = (1 - p) \frac{1 - \rho}{\rho}, \quad (\text{A27})$$

which implies the variance inflation

$$\text{Var}(D) = np(1 - p)[1 + (n - 1)\rho]. \quad (\text{A28})$$

We keep the same interval estimators as in the Binomial benchmark, namely Clopper–Pearson, Jeffreys equal-tailed, and the normal approximation (Wald), computed under independence, and we evaluate empirical 95% coverage under Beta–Binomial sampling.

Results. Table A3 reports results for the baseline configuration across increasing values of ρ . As ρ rises, the dispersion of the realized bounds increases, consistent with the variance inflation in (A28).

(a) Jeffreys

(b) Normal

(c) Clopper-Pearson

Figure A8: Empirical coverage over $p \in [0, 1]$ for nominal 95% equal-tailed intervals ($n = 50$, $S = 10,000$).

At the same time, average interval lengths do not increase commensurately because the intervals are computed under Binomial assumptions and therefore do not incorporate ρ . Figure A9 shows the direct consequence, empirical coverage declines monotonically with ρ for all three procedures. Figure A10 reports coverage as a function of p under fixed clustering ($\rho = 0.05$), the stepwise patterns reflect discreteness, and the normal approximation displays the largest distortions at low PDs.

Taken together, the experiment isolates the effect of within-grade dependence, when outcomes follow a Beta–Binomial law, Binomial-based intervals constructed under independence do not adapt to the inflated sampling variability and can therefore fall below the nominal level. This should be interpreted as a sensitivity result to over-dispersion rather than as a numerical artifact. In applications, this motivates pairing Binomial-based calibration intervals with dedicated within-grade homogeneity or over-dispersion diagnostics, as required in IRB validation practice (e.g., CRR Article 170(3)(c)) and emphasized by supervisory reviews such as TRIM (ECB, 2021).

Table A3: Baseline scenario (Beta–Binomial). For each clustering level ρ and each method, we report the Monte Carlo mean interval $[\bar{L}, \bar{U}]$, together with the Monte Carlo standard deviations of the bounds (second line), and the mean interval length $\bar{\ell} = \bar{U} - \bar{L}$.

ρ	Clopper–Pearson (exact)		Jeffreys (equal-tailed)		Normal (Wald)	
	$[\bar{L}, \bar{U}]$	$\bar{\ell}$	$[\bar{L}, \bar{U}]$	$\bar{\ell}$	$[\bar{L}, \bar{U}]$	$\bar{\ell}$
0.00	[0.0049, 0.0183] (0.0022, 0.0041)	0.0134	[0.0053, 0.0177] (0.0022, 0.0041)	0.0124	[0.0040, 0.0162] (0.0022, 0.0041)	0.0122
0.01	[0.0055, 0.0175] (0.0075, 0.0129)	0.0120	[0.0058, 0.0167] (0.0075, 0.0130)	0.0110	[0.0048, 0.0151] (0.0073, 0.0132)	0.0103
0.05	[0.0070, 0.0167] (0.0184, 0.0264)	0.0097	[0.0071, 0.0158] (0.0185, 0.0266)	0.0086	[0.0066, 0.0138] (0.0183, 0.0269)	0.0072
0.10	[0.0074, 0.0157] (0.0268, 0.0353)	0.0083	[0.0076, 0.0147] (0.0269, 0.0354)	0.0072	[0.0072, 0.0126] (0.0267, 0.0358)	0.0054

Note: In each interval cell, the first line reports the Monte Carlo mean bounds $[\bar{L}, \bar{U}]$, the second line reports the Monte Carlo standard deviations of the lower and upper bounds, respectively.

Figure A9: Empirical coverage (nominal 95%) as a function of clustering ρ , baseline configuration, intervals computed under Binomial formulas.

Figure A10: Empirical coverage (nominal 95%) as a function of p , with $n = 100$ and $\rho = 0.05$, intervals computed under Binomial formulas.

G Asymptotic convergence of the Jeffreys and Clopper–Pearson upper bounds

We provide here a detailed asymptotic analysis of the behavior of the Jeffreys and Clopper–Pearson upper bounds in the zero-default setting. The Clopper–Pearson upper bound, denoted p_{CP} , satisfies:

$$(1 - p_{\text{CP}})^n = \alpha, \quad (\text{A29})$$

which leads to the closed-form expression:

$$p_{\text{CP}} = 1 - \alpha^{1/n}. \quad (\text{A30})$$

Using a first-order Taylor expansion of $\alpha^{1/n}$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, we obtain:

$$\alpha^{1/n} = 1 - \frac{\log(1/\alpha)}{n} + o\left(\frac{1}{n}\right), \quad (\text{A31})$$

and thus:

$$p_{\text{CP}} \approx \frac{\log(1/\alpha)}{n}. \quad (\text{A32})$$

For the Jeffreys approach, the upper bound p_{Jeffreys} corresponds to the $(1 - \alpha)$ quantile of the Beta $(\frac{1}{2}, n + \frac{1}{2})$ distribution. A standard result asserts that if $X \sim \text{Beta}(a, b)$ with a fixed and $b \rightarrow \infty$, then:

$$bX \xrightarrow{d} \text{Gamma}(a, 1), \quad (\text{A33})$$

where \xrightarrow{d} denotes convergence in distribution.

This result follows from the representation of a Beta random variable as the ratio of two independent Gamma random variables:

$$X = \frac{G_1}{G_1 + G_2}, \quad (\text{A34})$$

where $G_1 \sim \text{Gamma}(a, 1)$ and $G_2 \sim \text{Gamma}(b, 1)$. As $b \rightarrow \infty$, G_2 dominates, which implies:

$$X \approx \frac{G_1}{G_2} \approx \frac{G_1}{b}, \quad (\text{A35})$$

and therefore:

$$bX \xrightarrow{d} G_1. \quad (\text{A36})$$

Applying this result to our setting, we obtain:

$$n p_{\text{Jeffreys}} \xrightarrow{d} \text{Gamma}\left(\frac{1}{2}, 1\right), \quad (\text{A37})$$

and consequently:

$$p_{\text{Jeffreys}} \approx \frac{q_{1-\alpha}}{n}, \quad (\text{A38})$$

where $q_{1-\alpha}$ denotes the $(1 - \alpha)$ quantile of the $\text{Gamma}\left(\frac{1}{2}, 1\right)$ distribution. Moreover, it can be shown that:

$$q_{1-\alpha} < \log(1/\alpha) \quad (\text{A39})$$

for typical values of α (e.g., $\alpha = 0.05$). Therefore, although both upper bounds decay at the same $O(1/n)$ rate, the Jeffreys bound has a smaller leading constant. This results in a sharper contraction of the posterior credible interval around zero when no defaults are observed. Figure A11 illustrates this phenomenon.

Figure A11: Upper bounds of the one-sided 95% intervals derived from the Jeffreys credible interval and the exact Clopper–Pearson method as a function of the sample size n , in the case of zero observed defaults. The Jeffreys upper bound (gold curve) contracts more rapidly toward zero than the Clopper–Pearson bound (black curve), reflecting greater statistical efficiency in sparse-data settings.

H Complement on the public corporate rating histories application

This appendix reports the full year-by-grade calibration diagnostics for the empirical application based on public S&P corporate rating histories. The main paper reports a reduced set of representative cells to illustrate the key regimes encountered in the data, namely zero-default investment-grade cohorts, low-default non-degenerate cohorts, and grades with moderate default counts. Table A4 below documents all year-by-grade default rates, benchmark TTC default rates, interval estimates, and Jeffreys posterior tail probabilities used in the analysis.

Table A4: Year-by-grade default rates and calibration diagnostics

Year	Grade	n	d	DR (%)	TTC (%)	Jeffreys CI (%)	Normal CI (%)	CP CI (%)	Jeffreys p -value
2012	AAA	15	0	0.000	0.000	[0.003, 15.182]	[0.000, 0.000]	[0.000, 21.802]	0.000
2012	AA	109	0	0.000	0.020	[0.000, 2.273]	[0.000, 0.000]	[0.000, 3.328]	0.166
2012	A	639	0	0.000	0.070	[0.000, 0.392]	[0.000, 0.000]	[0.000, 0.576]	0.656
2012	BBB	1083	0	0.000	0.220	[0.000, 0.232]	[0.000, 0.000]	[0.000, 0.340]	0.971
2012	BB	738	1	0.136	0.860	[0.015, 0.632]	[0.000, 0.401]	[0.003, 0.753]	0.995
2012	B	1137	8	0.704	4.280	[0.333, 1.323]	[0.218, 1.189]	[0.304, 1.382]	1.000
2012	C	88	22	25.000	26.850	[16.860, 34.753]	[15.953, 34.047]	[16.378, 35.368]	0.646
2013	AAA	14	0	0.000	0.000	[0.003, 16.155]	[0.000, 0.000]	[0.000, 23.164]	0.000
2013	AA	111	0	0.000	0.020	[0.000, 2.233]	[0.000, 0.000]	[0.000, 3.269]	0.167
2013	A	575	0	0.000	0.070	[0.000, 0.436]	[0.000, 0.000]	[0.000, 0.639]	0.631
2013	BBB	1177	0	0.000	0.220	[0.000, 0.213]	[0.000, 0.000]	[0.000, 0.313]	0.977
2013	BB	735	1	0.136	0.860	[0.015, 0.634]	[0.000, 0.403]	[0.003, 0.756]	0.995
2013	B	1333	7	0.525	4.280	[0.235, 1.028]	[0.137, 0.913]	[0.211, 1.079]	1.000
2013	C	103	29	28.155	26.850	[20.162, 37.357]	[19.470, 36.841]	[19.735, 37.873]	0.377
2014	AAA	14	0	0.000	0.000	[0.003, 16.155]	[0.000, 0.000]	[0.000, 23.164]	0.000
2014	AA	109	0	0.000	0.020	[0.000, 2.273]	[0.000, 0.000]	[0.000, 3.328]	0.166
2014	A	567	0	0.000	0.070	[0.000, 0.442]	[0.000, 0.000]	[0.000, 0.648]	0.627
2014	BBB	1193	0	0.000	0.220	[0.000, 0.210]	[0.000, 0.000]	[0.000, 0.309]	0.978
2014	BB	759	1	0.132	0.860	[0.014, 0.614]	[0.000, 0.390]	[0.003, 0.732]	0.996
2014	B	1475	7	0.475	4.280	[0.213, 0.930]	[0.124, 0.825]	[0.191, 0.975]	1.000
2014	C	99	23	23.232	26.850	[15.762, 32.242]	[14.913, 31.551]	[15.333, 32.793]	0.790
2015	AAA	12	0	0.000	0.000	[0.004, 18.531]	[0.000, 0.000]	[0.000, 26.465]	0.000
2015	AA	115	0	0.000	0.020	[0.000, 2.156]	[0.000, 0.000]	[0.000, 3.157]	0.170
2015	A	645	0	0.000	0.070	[0.000, 0.389]	[0.000, 0.000]	[0.000, 0.570]	0.658
2015	BBB	1266	0	0.000	0.220	[0.000, 0.198]	[0.000, 0.000]	[0.000, 0.291]	0.982
2015	BB	880	1	0.114	0.860	[0.012, 0.530]	[0.000, 0.336]	[0.003, 0.631]	0.998
2015	B	1533	15	0.978	4.280	[0.573, 1.568]	[0.486, 1.471]	[0.549, 1.609]	1.000
2015	C	108	19	17.593	26.850	[11.315, 25.580]	[10.412, 24.774]	[10.937, 26.102]	0.988
2016	AAA	12	0	0.000	0.000	[0.004, 18.531]	[0.000, 0.000]	[0.000, 26.465]	0.000
2016	AA	123	0	0.000	0.020	[0.000, 2.017]	[0.000, 0.000]	[0.000, 2.955]	0.176
2016	A	645	0	0.000	0.070	[0.000, 0.389]	[0.000, 0.000]	[0.000, 0.570]	0.658

Continued on next page

Year	Grade	n	d	DR (%)	TTC (%)	Jeffreys CI (%)	Normal CI (%)	CP CI (%)	Jeffreys p -value
2016	BBB	1265	0	0.000	0.220	[0.000, 0.198]	[0.000, 0.000]	[0.000, 0.291]	0.982
2016	BB	917	2	0.218	0.860	[0.045, 0.698]	[0.000, 0.520]	[0.026, 0.786]	0.993
2016	B	1407	29	2.061	4.280	[1.414, 2.905]	[1.319, 2.804]	[1.385, 2.947]	1.000
2016	C	146	34	23.288	26.850	[16.999, 30.623]	[16.432, 30.144]	[16.698, 30.993]	0.834
2017	AAA	8	0	0.000	0.000	[0.006, 26.222]	[0.000, 0.000]	[0.000, 36.942]	0.000
2017	AA	108	0	0.000	0.020	[0.000, 2.294]	[0.000, 0.000]	[0.000, 3.358]	0.165
2017	A	625	0	0.000	0.070	[0.000, 0.401]	[0.000, 0.000]	[0.000, 0.588]	0.651
2017	BBB	1234	0	0.000	0.220	[0.000, 0.203]	[0.000, 0.000]	[0.000, 0.298]	0.980
2017	BB	919	0	0.000	0.860	[0.000, 0.273]	[0.000, 0.000]	[0.000, 0.401]	1.000
2017	B	1350	3	0.222	4.280	[0.063, 0.592]	[0.000, 0.473]	[0.046, 0.648]	1.000
2017	C	172	34	19.767	26.850	[14.348, 26.194]	[13.816, 25.719]	[14.095, 26.512]	0.984
2018	AAA	5	0	0.000	0.000	[0.009, 37.938]	[0.000, 0.000]	[0.000, 52.182]	0.000
2018	AA	92	0	0.000	0.020	[0.001, 2.686]	[0.000, 0.000]	[0.000, 3.930]	0.152
2018	A	572	0	0.000	0.070	[0.000, 0.438]	[0.000, 0.000]	[0.000, 0.643]	0.629
2018	BBB	1088	0	0.000	0.220	[0.000, 0.231]	[0.000, 0.000]	[0.000, 0.338]	0.971
2018	BB	850	0	0.000	0.860	[0.000, 0.295]	[0.000, 0.000]	[0.000, 0.433]	1.000
2018	B	1443	6	0.416	4.280	[0.174, 0.855]	[0.084, 0.748]	[0.153, 0.903]	1.000
2018	C	136	33	24.265	26.850	[17.652, 31.959]	[17.060, 31.469]	[17.329, 32.355]	0.749
2019	AAA	3	0	0.000	0.000	[0.015, 53.558]	[0.000, 0.000]	[0.000, 70.760]	0.000
2019	AA	50	0	0.000	0.020	[0.001, 4.876]	[0.000, 0.000]	[0.000, 7.112]	0.113
2019	A	375	0	0.000	0.070	[0.000, 0.667]	[0.000, 0.000]	[0.000, 0.979]	0.532
2019	BBB	626	2	0.319	0.220	[0.066, 1.021]	[0.000, 0.762]	[0.039, 1.149]	0.262
2019	BB	581	2	0.344	0.860	[0.072, 1.100]	[0.000, 0.820]	[0.042, 1.238]	0.925
2019	B	1097	14	1.276	4.280	[0.733, 2.075]	[0.612, 1.940]	[0.699, 2.132]	1.000
2019	C	120	22	18.333	26.850	[12.207, 25.965]	[11.410, 25.256]	[11.861, 26.431]	0.985
2020	AAA	2	0	0.000	0.000	[0.022, 66.682]	[0.000, 0.000]	[0.000, 84.189]	0.000
2020	AA	28	0	0.000	0.020	[0.002, 8.507]	[0.000, 0.000]	[0.000, 12.344]	0.085
2020	A	208	0	0.000	0.070	[0.000, 1.199]	[0.000, 0.000]	[0.000, 1.758]	0.411
2020	BBB	320	0	0.000	0.220	[0.000, 0.781]	[0.000, 0.000]	[0.000, 1.146]	0.765
2020	BB	335	4	1.194	0.860	[0.404, 2.814]	[0.031, 2.357]	[0.326, 3.029]	0.236
2020	B	681	22	3.231	4.280	[2.094, 4.763]	[1.903, 4.558]	[2.035, 4.850]	0.916
2020	C	143	61	42.657	26.850	[34.765, 50.843]	[34.551, 50.764]	[34.431, 51.194]	0.000

Note: This table reports year-by-grade one-year default rates and calibration diagnostics for the S&P corporate cohorts over a 12-month horizon. All rates and interval bounds are expressed in percent. The Jeffreys p -value is defined as $\Pr(p \leq \text{TTC} \mid d, n)$ under the Jeffreys posterior. The main result is that many investment-grade cells correspond to zero- or low-default cases, for which the Normal interval degenerates to $[0, 0]$, whereas Jeffreys and Clopper–Pearson remain well-defined and provide positive upper bounds. Differences across methods become much smaller when default counts are moderate.

I Complement on the public mortgage portfolio application

This appendix documents the implementation choices used in the public mortgage portfolio application. The pipeline is designed to preserve a strict out-of-time protocol: every data-adaptive object, including imputation statistics, category definitions, discretization rules, encodings, probability calibration, and grade cutoffs, is learned on the Train period and then reused unchanged for Validation and OOS. The purpose is to make the full workflow auditable and reproducible.

I.1 Data files, key fields, and outcome definition

The Freddie Mac Single-Family Loan-Level Dataset is provided as two pipe-delimited files without header rows: an *Origination* file, with one row per loan at acquisition, and a *Monthly Performance* file, with one row per loan per month. Dates are month-level (YYYYMM), and several fields use masking codes (e.g., 999/99/9999) that are treated as missing. We apply column names programmatically at load time. Origination information available at approval is merged with monthly performance records using the loan sequence number as the unique loan identifier. Monthly performance records are used to construct the 12-month default indicator, while predictors are restricted to information available at origination. For completeness, the full Freddie Mac data dictionary is included in the public replication package.

Key fields used in this paper. Table A5 lists the subset of fields used either as origination predictors or to engineer the outcome from monthly performance records.

Outcome definition. The binary target Y indicates whether a loan experiences a default event within the forecasting horizon ($T = 12$ months) starting from the *first payment date*. The outcome is engineered exclusively from the Monthly Performance file and is defined as

$$Y = \mathbb{1}\{\text{default within } T \text{ months}\}.$$

A loan is flagged as defaulted if at least one monthly record within the first T months satisfies one of the following conditions: (i) the delinquency bucket is greater than or equal to 3 under the MBA method, corresponding to 90+ days past due, (ii) the delinquency status equals RA, indicating REO acquisition, or (iii) the zero-balance code is in $\{02, 03, 09\}$, corresponding to liquidation or termination events. The default indicator is set to one at the first occurrence of any of these events within the 12-month horizon, and to zero otherwise.

Prepayment and early termination. Mortgages may terminate early because of prepayment or other non-default reasons. In the baseline implementation, loans whose performance history ends before month T without any default-triggering event are retained and treated as non-defaults over the 12-month horizon. This convention avoids conditioning the validation sample on ex-post survival up to month T and is kept fixed across Train, Validation, and OOS samples.

Table A5: Key fields used from the Freddie Mac data dictionary.

Field	Definition (used in this paper)	Type / missing codes
<i>Origination file (one row per loan)</i>		
Credit score	Borrower credit score at acquisition.	Numeric; 9999=NA
Original UPB	UPB at note date (rounded).	Numeric
LTV / CLTV	Original loan-to-value and combined LTV at note date.	Numeric; 999=NA
DTI	Debt-to-income ratio at underwriting.	Numeric; 999=NA
Interest rate	Note rate at origination.	Numeric (decimal)
Loan term	Scheduled number of monthly payments.	Numeric
Occupancy status	Primary / second home / investment.	Alpha; 9=NA
Property type	SF/Condo/PUD/Co-op/MH.	Alpha; 99=NA
State	Property state code.	Alpha
First-time homebuyer flag	First-time homebuyer indicator.	Alpha; 9=NA
Loan purpose	Purchase / refinance (cash-out / no cash-out).	Alpha; 9=NA
Channel	Retail/Broker/Correspondent/TPO.	Alpha; 9=NA
MI%	Mortgage insurance percentage at purchase.	Numeric; 999=NA
<i>Monthly Performance file (one row per loan per month)</i>		
Loan sequence number	Unique loan identifier (join key).	Alphanumeric
Monthly reporting period	As-of month (YYYYMM).	Date (YYYYMM)
Delinquency status	MBA delinquency bucket; RA indicates REO acquisition.	Alphanumeric
Zero balance code / date	Termination reason and effective month.	Numeric / Date
Current actual UPB	Ending principal balance for the month.	Numeric

Note: The complete Freddie Mac data dictionary, including all fields, lengths, and masking conventions, is provided in the replication package.

I.2 Out-of-time protocol and split roles

Split roles. The workflow uses an explicit quarter-based split, where vintages are indexed by origination quarter. The Train window covers 2008Q1–2019Q4, the internal Validation window covers 2020Q1–2021Q4, and the strictly held-out OOS block covers 2022Q1–2023Q4. The Validation block is used as a development holdout for predictive assessment, while the OOS block is reserved for final backtesting diagnostics. All preprocessing objects, encodings, probability calibration steps, and grade cutoffs are learned on the Train window and then reused unchanged for Validation and OOS.

Table A6 summarizes the time split used in the mortgage application.

Table A6: Empirical design summary for the public mortgage application

Block	Calendar quarters	Loans	Defaults	Default rate
Train	2008Q1–2019Q4	19 305 058	110 097	0.5703%
Validation	2020Q1–2021Q4	8 010 133	54 343	0.6784%
Development window (Train+Validation)	2008Q1–2021Q4	27 315 191	164 440	0.6018%
OOS backtesting	2022Q1–2023Q4	Used only for backtesting		

Note: The OOS block is strictly held out and used only to compute backtesting diagnostics.

I.3 Preprocessing: imputation and supervised discretization

Feature definition. A fixed feature set is defined from the Train data. Predictors are restricted to information available at origination. The main origination predictors include credit score, original balance, LTV/CLTV, DTI, interest rate, loan term, occupancy status, loan purpose, origination channel, and basic geographic information. Masking codes (e.g., 999/99/9999) are converted to missing prior to preprocessing. When a predictor is absent in a later vintage, it is treated as missing and handled by the Train-based imputation rule. Identifier-like variables not intended for prediction are excluded to avoid spurious time effects driven by changes in data availability.

Imputation. Missing values are imputed using deterministic rules computed on Train:

$$x_j \leftarrow \begin{cases} \text{median}_{\text{Train}}(x_j) & \text{if } x_j \text{ is numeric,} \\ \text{mode}_{\text{Train}}(x_j) & \text{if } x_j \text{ is categorical.} \end{cases}$$

For a small subset of core origination drivers, we also consider a cohort-based median imputation estimated on Train, for example by vintage and origination purpose, with explicit fallbacks to broader groups and then the global Train median. This variant is used for robustness checks.

Missingness indicators (robustness). As an alternative specification, missingness indicators are added for selected drivers. They are computed from raw inputs prior to imputation and therefore

do not use future information.

Supervised discretization. Predictors are discretized using a supervised procedure estimated on Train and then applied unchanged out-of-time. Discretization reduces sensitivity to outliers and supports stable risk ordering.

Construction and constraints. For each predictor x_j , discretization yields a bin label

$$x_j \mapsto b_j(x_j) \in \{-1, 0, 1, \dots, B_j - 1\},$$

where -1 denotes a dedicated missing-value bin and the remaining labels correspond to non-missing bins. The partition is selected to maximize class separation under a Gini-based criterion. The baseline specification sets $B_j \leq 10$ and enforces a minimum bin size of 300 observations on Train. For numerical predictors, candidate cutpoints come from a fixed grid of Train quantiles (50 quantiles). For categorical predictors, levels are ordered by their Train default rate and then grouped under the same objective and size constraints; missing categories are treated as an explicit level.

Monotonicity. After the initial partition, adjacent bins are merged until the empirical default rate is monotone across the ordered non-missing bins. Monotonicity is enforced in the direction implied by the global trend, based on the endpoints, which stabilizes the subsequent score construction in low-default settings.

I.4 Model development: estimation, calibration, and master scale

Design matrix from bins (Train-only). Binned predictors are converted into numerical inputs through a smoothed log-odds, WOE-style encoding computed on Train. For predictor j and bin c , let

$$d_{j,c} = \sum_{i \in \text{Train}} \mathbb{1}\{Y_i = 1, b_j(x_i) = c\}, \quad n_{j,c} = \sum_{i \in \text{Train}} \mathbb{1}\{Y_i = 0, b_j(x_i) = c\}.$$

Each bin is mapped to

$$z_j(c) = \log\left(\frac{d_{j,c} + s}{n_{j,c} + s}\right),$$

with a fixed smoothing constant $s = 0.5$. The encoding map is fixed after Train; an unseen bin out-of-time receives the smoothed global Train log-odds. To reduce redundancy, we filter highly correlated encoded drivers using an absolute correlation threshold of 0.85 computed on Train.

Regularized logistic regression. Let Z denote the resulting design matrix. We estimate an ℓ_2 -penalized logistic regression,

$$\Pr(Y = 1 \mid Z) = \sigma(\beta_0 + Z^\top \beta), \quad \sigma(u) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-u}},$$

with regularization parameter C and solver `lbfgs`.

Time-aware tuning and calibration. Hyperparameter selection for C is performed by time-aware cross-validation on the Train window, using out-of-fold log-loss as the criterion. We use 5 folds and an expanding-window time scheme over quarterly vintages. Probability calibration is fitted on a time-last split of Train using isotonic regression and then applied unchanged to Validation and OOS. This probability calibration step is used for score construction and ranking; grade-level TTC PDs used for backtesting are subsequently defined as realized default frequencies on the Train window.

Master scale and TTC benchmarks (fit on Train). A monotone TTC score is computed from the uncalibrated log-odds and mapped into $K = 10$ ordered grades using quantile-based edges estimated on Train only. The grade cutoffs are then kept fixed for Validation and OOS. Grade-level TTC benchmarks are computed as realized 12-month default frequencies on the Train window:

$$\text{PD}_k^{\text{TTC}} = \frac{d_k}{n_k}, \quad k = 1, \dots, K,$$

where (n_k, d_k) are exposure and default counts aggregated within grade k .

Table A7 reports the full master scale, including the score ranges omitted from the main text for conciseness.

Table A7: Master scale grades with score ranges (Train sample)

Grade	Min score	Max score	n_k	d_k	PD $_k$ (%)
1	749	851	1 509 002	564	0.0374
2	726	748	1 546 961	1 158	0.0749
3	709	725	1 586 588	2 047	0.1290
4	695	708	1 537 786	3 015	0.1961
5	683	694	1 464 651	4 132	0.2821
6	670	682	1 637 137	6 271	0.3830
7	658	669	1 509 211	7 830	0.5188
8	644	657	1 655 201	12 042	0.7275
9	627	643	1 630 916	16 802	1.0302
10	506	626	1 767 435	31 490	1.7817

Note: Higher scores correspond to lower credit risk. Grade 1 is the safest grade and Grade 10 the riskiest. The score cutoffs are fitted on Train only and then held fixed for Validation and OOS backtesting.

Replication materials. The replication package provides the complete command sequence, configuration files, fixed hyperparameters, and versioned software environment required to reproduce all tables and figures. The main entrypoints are provided through a dedicated Makefile

(`replication/Makefile`). From the repository root, the full paper replication is run with `make -f replication/Makefile paper_all`. For the mortgage application only, `make -f replication/Makefile pipeline` runs the end-to-end workflow (labels \rightarrow preprocessing \rightarrow training \rightarrow reporting and OOS diagnostics).

Sample characteristics. The development sample (Train+Validation) contains approximately 27.3 million loans. The unconditional 12-month default rate is about 0.6%, which motivates a regularized specification and a conservative out-of-time preprocessing design.

Table A8: Descriptive statistics (Train+Validation sample).

Variable	N	Mean	SD	P25–P75	Min–Max
Credit score	27 311 359	753.379	46.019	724–790	333–842
Mortgage insurance percent	27 315 104	4.774	10.170	0–0	0–52
Number of units	27 313 147	1.026	0.214	1–1	1–4
Combined loan-to-value (CLTV)	27 314 687	72.870	20.182	61–83	1–728
Debt-to-income (DTI)	24 416 141	33.497	10.122	26–42	1–65
Original UPB	27 315 191	239 480.653	130 918.098	140 000–317 000	10 000–1 500 000
Loan-to-value (LTV)	27 314 793	71.794	19.649	60–80	1–728
Original interest rate	27 315 191	3.965	0.923	3.250–4.625	1.500–8.750
Original loan term (months)	27 315 191	314.691	76.278	240–360	60–559
Number of borrowers	27 314 232	1.527	0.507	1–2	1–5
First-time homebuyer (0/1)	27 312 023	0.127	–	–	0–1
Prepayment penalty flag (0/1)	27 315 191	0.000	–	–	0–1
Super conforming flag (0/1)	906 451	1.000	–	–	0–1
Relief refinance indicator (0/1)	2 865 501	1.000	–	–	0–1
Interest-only indicator (0/1)	27 315 191	0.000	–	–	0–1
MI cancellation indicator (0/1)	3 840 621	0.242	–	–	0–1
Default (0/1)	27 315 191	0.006	–	–	0–1

Note: For continuous variables we report the number of non-missing observations (N), mean, standard deviation (SD), the interquartile range (P25–P75), and the full range (Min–Max). For binary indicators, the mean corresponds to the proportion of ones; dispersion and quantiles are not reported.

Table A9: ℓ_2 -penalized logistic regression (cross-time validated): coefficients and predictive metrics.

Variable	Coefficient	Odds ratio
Intercept	0.1643	1.179
Score \times DTI (interaction)	-0.1179	0.889
Score \times CLTV (interaction)	-0.1118	0.894
CLTV \times DTI (interaction)	-0.0631	0.939
Original DTI (WOE)	-0.3326	0.717
Original loan term (WOE)	0.8429	2.323
Original LTV (WOE)	-0.0102	0.990
Number of borrowers (WOE)	1.0710	2.918
Property state (WOE)	0.6795	1.973
MI percent (WOE)	0.1086	1.115
Origination channel (WOE)	0.9916	2.696
Original UPB (WOE)	-0.2000	0.819
Loan purpose (WOE)	-0.5555	0.574
Number of units (WOE)	-0.5837	0.558
Occupancy status (WOE)	-0.7725	0.462
Property type (WOE)	-0.7176	0.488
Special eligibility program (WOE)	-0.8591	0.424
Model Metrics		
N (Train / Validation)	19,305,058 / 8,010,133	
# Defaults (Train / Validation)	110,097 / 54,343	
Default Rate (Train / Validation)	0.5703% / 0.6784%	
AUC (Train / Validation)	0.7909 / 0.7347	
Gini (Train / Validation)	0.5817 / 0.4694	
LogLoss (Train / Validation)	0.0324 / 0.0383	
Brier Score (Train / Validation)	0.005620 / 0.006702	
ECE (Train / Validation)	0.002687 / 0.000785	

Note: The regularization parameter C is selected using *cross-time* (time-based) cross-validation. Predictors are WOE-transformed unless stated otherwise. Coefficients are on the log-odds scale; odds ratios are $\exp(\beta)$. Since coefficients are estimated under ℓ_2 regularization and the penalty level is selected in a data-driven way, conventional coefficient-wise standard errors and frequentist p -values are not reported.

J Supplementary empirical application

This appendix reports an additional empirical application conducted on proprietary bank data. The main paper already presents two empirical applications based on data that can be described in full. Here, we include a third application to retain empirical insights obtained in an operational IRB setting while respecting confidentiality constraints. Relative to the mortgage-portfolio application in the main text, this dataset is materially smaller, which makes it informative for understanding how the proposed calibration and backtesting procedures behave on portfolios of more modest size. Accordingly, we provide the modelling set-up and the validation outputs required to interpret the results, while restricting the description of the underlying data to non-identifying information.

J.1 Setting and data

We replicate the main steps of a bank’s IRB approach, risk differentiation and risk quantification, to build an IRB-compliant PD model in the spirit of [Fraisie and Laporte \(2022\)](#). We then assess the calibrated PDs using frequentist methods, binomial confidence intervals based on the normal approximation and the exact Clopper–Pearson method, and the Jeffreys credible interval.

The analysis relies on a proprietary dataset of auto-leasing contracts provided by a European commercial bank. The target variable, *Default*, is binary and equals one if the borrower defaults within the first 12 months after origination, and zero otherwise. To mitigate disclosure risks, and to reduce the impact of severe class imbalance on estimation and validation, we fix the event rate to 5% by randomly undersampling non-default observations, following standard practice in rare-event modelling and validation ([Brown and Mues, 2012](#); [Fitzpatrick and Mues, 2016](#); [Chen et al., 2024](#)). The dataset contains 10 predictors capturing both borrower characteristics (e.g., age, marital status, housing status, employment duration) and contract attributes (e.g., vehicle value, amount financed, down payment, maturity, instalment burden relative to income).

After undersampling, the dataset contains 6,265 anonymized loan contracts. [Table A10](#) reports descriptive statistics for the key explanatory variables and the default indicator. A representative contract finances the purchase of a €13,000 vehicle, with an average funded amount close to €11,000 and a contractual maturity of about 55 months. Borrowers are on average 46 years old, most are married, most are not homeowners, and average job tenure is approximately ten years. Repayments represent about 10% of monthly income, down payments are typically below 50% of the vehicle value, and most borrowers have no recorded credit events in the six months preceding origination.

Standard preprocessing steps were applied, including exploratory data analysis. First, correlations between the variables were computed, and pairs with correlation coefficients higher than 0.7 were further examined using the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) to assess multicollinearity. The variable with the lowest VIF was retained in the final model, while the others were excluded to reduce collinearity and improve model stability. Next, all continuous variables were discretized into categorical variables using a binning procedure that maximizes the Gini coefficient, with a maximum of 5 bins, as in [Fraisie and Laporte \(2022\)](#). One-hot encoding was then applied to both the discretized

Table A10: Descriptive statistics

Variable	Count	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	25%	Median	75%	Max
Job tenure (years)	6265	10.018	10.171	0.000	2.000	6.000	16.000	58.000
Age (years)	6265	46.067	14.293	18.000	35.000	47.000	56.000	88.000
Car price (€)	6265	12867	6170	546	8102	11950	16480	47051
Funding amount (€)	6265	11097	5827	546	6599	10040	14500	30000
Loan duration (months)	6265	55.064	19.332	6.000	48.000	60.000	72.000	96.000
Monthly payment (% income)	6265	0.102	0.061	0.005	0.067	0.092	0.126	2.630
Down payment (% car price)	6265	0.101	–	0.000	–	–	–	1.000
Credit event (0/1)	6265	0.015	–	0.000	–	–	–	1.000
Married (0/1)	6265	0.568	–	0.000	–	–	–	1.000
Homeowner (0/1)	6265	0.417	–	0.000	–	–	–	1.000
Default (0/1)	6265	0.050	–	0.000	–	–	–	1.000

Note: This table reports descriptive statistics for the explanatory variables and the target. For binary features, standard errors and quartiles are omitted and denoted by "–". Monetary values are expressed in euros.

continuous variables and all categorical variables.

Finally, the dataset is partitioned into two mutually exclusive, stratified subsets. Ninety percent of the data is utilized for the risk differentiation and quantification phases, while the remaining ten percent serves as a validation set, dedicated solely to backtesting the predicted probabilities of default (PDs). To ensure robust model development, 90% of the data is further divided into a training set (comprising 80% of the total data) for fitting the scoring models, and a test set (comprising 10%), which is used to evaluate model performance and select the final specification. The calibrated PDs are computed on the full development set, which includes both the training and test subsets (90% in total). The 5% default rate is maintained across all three subsets through stratified sampling. The overall data partitioning and validation workflow is illustrated in Figure A12.

J.2 PD model development and risk segmentation

We then apply the IRB methodology outlined in Section 1 of the main paper to develop and calibrate a probability of default (PD) model.

Risk differentiation. Among the various alternatives for estimating the conditional probability of default, logistic regression is a widely used model in credit scoring, especially in the banking sector, due to its robustness and interpretability. To optimize model performance, features were selected using an automatic stepwise procedure, ensuring that only the most significant variables were retained. All models were trained on the dataset and their performance assessed using a separate test set. Additional details regarding the model implementation and estimation process are available in the code repository associated with this article.

Table A11 presents the results of the final logistic regression model. The marginal effects of the key variables on the probability of default are as follows. The negative coefficient for *Down payment*

Figure A12: Blocks in grey represent model development steps: risk differentiation and quantification. The blue-grey block corresponds to the validation phase. \hat{y} denotes the predicted probability of default from the model; y refers to the actual observed default indicator.

(-1.328) indicates that larger down payments reduce the likelihood of default. Specifically, an increase in the down payment lowers the log-odds of default, suggesting a direct relationship between borrower commitment and reduced default risk. The positive coefficient for *Credit event* (1.942) shows that a history of credit events significantly raises the likelihood of default, with each credit event substantially increasing the probability of future default. Similarly, *Homeowner* has a negative coefficient (-0.846), implying that borrowers who own their home are less likely to default, likely due to increased financial stability. Lastly, *Funding amount* exhibits a positive effect on the default probability (0.740), meaning that larger loans are associated with higher default risk. This is intuitive, as higher loan amounts may indicate a higher debt burden, and an increased likelihood of default.

To build the *risk grades*, we apply a quantile-based binning procedure to the predicted probabilities of default. This method was selected for its simplicity and practical interpretability, which enhances its utility in real-world applications. The segmentation is performed jointly on both the training and test datasets, which improves the stability of default rate estimates within each group. We adopt a four-bin quantile approach, balancing granularity and stability. The Chi-squared test and the Kruskal–Wallis test both confirm significant heterogeneity in default rates across the resulting groups.

Risk quantification. The probability of default (PD) for each risk grade is estimated as the average default probability of individuals within that grade, using both the training and test datasets. This approach mirrors the methodology commonly employed by banks to calculate long-run averages in practice.

Table A11: Stepwise Logistic Regression Results

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Err.	z-stat	Pr > z
Intercept (const)	-2.034***	0.214	-9.493	0.000
Down payment	-1.328**	0.514	-2.586	0.010
Credit event	1.942***	0.302	6.431	0.000
Homeowner	-0.846***	0.176	-4.797	0.000
Job tenure (disc. 1)	-0.449**	0.226	-1.984	0.047
Job tenure (disc. 2)	-0.838***	0.158	-5.304	0.000
Job tenure (disc. 3)	-1.420***	0.228	-6.216	0.000
Age (disc. 1)	-0.687***	0.180	-3.820	0.000
Funding amount (disc. 1)	0.741***	0.160	4.644	0.000
Loan duration (disc. 1)	0.507***	0.158	3.220	0.001
Monthly payment (disc. 1)	0.287*	0.156	1.840	0.066
Model Metrics				
AUC (Area Under the Curve)	0.792			
Brier Score	0.042			
Log Loss	0.165			
Expected Calibration Error (ECE)	0.009			
AIC (Akaike Information Criterion)	1741.080			

Note: Results of the stepwise logistic regression model for estimating the probability of default, including coefficients, standard errors, z-statistics, p-values, and model performance metrics. Discretized variables are indicated by the "disc" notation. * $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.01$

J.3 Backtesting the PD Model

We now backtest the previously developed PD model using the validation set, which was held out entirely during model development and calibration. The PD model, constructed during the risk differentiation and quantification phases, is applied to the validation data. The procedure involves the following steps: applying the estimated logistic regression model to the validation sample, classifying individuals into risk grades based on predefined PD thresholds, and assigning to each grade the corresponding average probability of default. The results of the PD model applied to the validation sample are presented in Table A12. Note that no defaults are observed in the backtesting sample for the first risk grade. Overall, the observed default frequencies in the validation sample are close to the calibrated PDs, suggesting that the model is well-calibrated and likely to pass validation.

To assess the calibration and conservatism of the predicted grade-level probabilities of default (PD_k), we compute both frequentist confidence intervals and Bayesian credible intervals. Calibration is primarily evaluated using equal-tailed (two-sided) intervals, while conservatism is specifically assessed through the one-sided Jeffreys interval, in accordance with the ECB's recommendations. The results of the PD backtesting are presented in Table A12, which reports the one-sided and two-sided Jeffreys intervals, the Clopper–Pearson interval, and the approximate normal interval. Overall, aside from Grade 1, the three methods produce broadly similar confidence intervals across

grades. The normal approximation systematically yields the narrowest intervals, reflecting its tendency to underestimate uncertainty in small or imbalanced samples. In contrast, the Clopper–Pearson method consistently delivers the widest intervals, owing to its exact and conservative construction, especially in the presence of sparse data. The Jeffreys intervals lie in between, offering a balanced compromise between informativeness and robustness. The differences between the methods become particularly salient in Grade 1, where no defaults are observed in the validation sample. In this zero-default setting, only the Jeffreys and Clopper–Pearson approaches produce non-degenerate intervals with positive upper bounds, thus properly accounting for the statistical uncertainty inherent to rare events. The normal approximation fails entirely in this case, yielding a collapsed upper bound at zero that contradicts basic prudential principles. This highlights the importance of using methods that remain valid under boundary cases, especially for regulatory backtesting, where the ability to quantify risk under extreme sparsity is critical.

Table A12: Confidence and credibility intervals by grade and method at 95% confidence level

Equal-Tailed Methods							
Grade	n_k	d_k	\hat{p}_k	PD_k	Jeffreys	Clopper–Pearson	Normal Approx.
[0, 0.015[163	0	0.000	0.008	[0.000, 0.015]	[0.000, 0.022]	[0.000, 0.000]
[0.015, 0.028[183	5	0.027	0.022	[0.010, 0.059]	[0.009, 0.063]	[0.004, 0.051]
[0.028, 0.062[139	7	0.050	0.046	[0.023, 0.096]	[0.020, 0.101]	[0.014, 0.087]
[0.062, 1]	142	20	0.141	0.132	[0.091, 0.205]	[0.088, 0.209]	[0.084, 0.198]
One-Sided Methods							
Grade	n_k	d_k	\hat{p}_k	PD_k	Jeffreys (ECB)	Clopper–Pearson	Normal Approx.
[0, 0.015[163	0	0.000	0.008	[0, 0.011]	[0, 0.018]	[0, 0.000]
[0.015, 0.028[183	5	0.027	0.022	[0, 0.053]	[0, 0.057]	[0, 0.047]
[0.028, 0.062[139	7	0.050	0.046	[0, 0.088]	[0, 0.092]	[0, 0.081]
[0.062, 1]	142	20	0.141	0.132	[0, 0.194]	[0, 0.198]	[0, 0.189]

Note: This table presents 95% confidence or credible intervals for the predicted probability of default (PD_k) across risk grades, based on the number of observations (n_k), the number of defaults (d_k), and the observed default rate (\hat{p}_k); equal-tailed intervals assess calibration, while one-sided intervals evaluate conservatism, using the Jeffreys (Bayesian), Clopper–Pearson (exact frequentist), and normal approximation (asymptotic) methods.

From a supervisory perspective, the Jeffreys one-sided interval (as defined by the ECB) is particularly relevant. It provides a conservative yet interpretable upper bound on the grade-level default probability, without overstating risk in better-performing segments. Its performance in Grade 1, where it produces a finite, data-informed bound in contrast to the degenerate result from the normal approximation, illustrates its robustness and suitability for IRB model validation. In summary, the table confirms that while approximate methods may suffice in well-populated risk grades, only exact or Bayesian intervals can provide reliable and interpretable results in low-default environments. The Jeffreys approach, in particular, stands out for its ability to maintain a balance between calibration and conservatism across all grades.

To complement the analysis, Table A13 presents the one-sided p -values from the Jeffreys test, following ECB recommendations for supervisory reporting (ECB, 2019). These values provide a measure of conservatism by quantifying the extent to which predicted PDs exceed what is supported by observed default data. A high p -value, such as 0.903 in grade 1, indicates that the PD is likely overstated relative to actual outcomes, reflecting a conservative stance. In contrast, lower p -values, for example, 0.298 in Grade 2, suggest a closer alignment between forecasted and realized default rates, potentially offering less prudential margin.

Table A13: Conservatism by grade: p -values from the Jeffreys test

Grade	n_k	d_k	\hat{p}_k	PD $_k$	p -value
[0, 0.015[163	0	0.000	0.008	0.903
[0.015, 0.028[183	5	0.027	0.022	0.298
[0.028, 0.062[139	7	0.050	0.046	0.385
[0.062, 1]	142	20	0.141	0.132	0.371

Note: This table reports one-sided p -values from the Jeffreys test used to assess conservatism; it also includes the number of observations (n_k), number of defaults (d_k), and observed default rate (\hat{p}_k) for each grade.

The results highlight that conservatism is not uniformly distributed across grades. In Grade 1, where no defaults are observed, the high p -value reflects strong conservatism, which is appropriate in the context of low-default portfolios. Grades 3 and 4 exhibit moderate values (0.385 and 0.371), pointing to a balanced calibration that incorporates a reasonable level of prudence. Grade 2 stands out with the lowest p -value, indicating that the prediction is closely aligned with observed defaults and may lack the cushion typically required by regulatory standards. Overall, the analysis confirms that the model behaves conservatively in the lowest-risk segment, remains adequately cautious in higher-risk buckets, but may require further review in the intermediate range to ensure compliance with supervisory expectations.

Finally, thanks to the Bayesian framework, we can directly quantify the uncertainty surrounding the default probability within each grade. Figure A13 displays the posterior distributions of the default probability p_k for the four risk grades. Grade 1 shows a sharp concentration near zero, consistent with the absence of observed defaults. The distributions shift progressively to the right from Grades 2 to 4, reflecting increasing observed default rates. Notably, the posterior for Grade 1 and 2 is more concentrated than those of Grades 3 and 4, due to a larger sample size that yields tighter inference around the true default probability. In contrast, Grades 3 and 4 exhibit wider posterior distributions, reflecting greater uncertainty stemming from smaller sample sizes.

Figure A13: Posterior distributions of the probability of default (p_k) by rating grade. Each curve represents the posterior Beta distribution within each grade.

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